

Application of Geometric Series and Maclaurin Series Relating to Taylor Series

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Abstract: This paper presents a novel idea to compute the Maclaurin series and Taylor series and also provides application of the geometric series and the Maclaurin series.

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1. Introduction

In the earlier days, geometric series [1-20] with positive exponents served as a vital role in the development of differential and integral calculus [38] and as an introduction to Maclaurin series, Taylor series and Fourier series [44]. Geometric series have significant applications in physics, engineering, biology, economics, finance, management, queueing theory, computer science and medicine [6]. Also, the product of geometric series [21-37] with prime numbers plays a vital in the sum of natural numbers and harmonic series [39-44].

2. Maclaurin Series

Taylor series is stated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &= f(a) + \frac{f'(a)}{1!}(x-a) + \frac{f''(a)}{2!}(x-a)^2 + \frac{f'''(a)}{3!}(x-a)^3 + \dots \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^{(n)}(a)}{n!}(x-a)^n. \end{aligned}$$

If $a = 0$ in the Taylor series, the Taylor series becomes the Maclaurin series:

$$f(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^{(n)}(0)}{n!}x^n = f(0) + \frac{f'(0)}{1!}x + \frac{f''(0)}{2!}x^2 + \frac{f'''(0)}{3!}x^3 + \dots$$

Let us prove these series using the following power series

$$f(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n x^n = a_0 + a_1 x + a_2 x^2 + a_3 x^3 + a_4 x^4 + a_5 x^5 + \dots$$

If $x = 0$ in the above power series, $f(0) = a_0$.

Now, let us differentiate the power series as follows:

$$f'(x) = a_1 + 2a_2 x + 3a_3 x^2 + 4a_4 x^3 + 5a_5 x^4 + \dots. \text{ If } x = 0 \text{ in } f'(x), f'(0) = a_1.$$

By differentiating $f'(x)$, we get

$$f''(x) = 2a_2 + 3 \times 2a_3 x + 4 \times 3a_4 x^2 + 5 \times 4a_5 x^3 + \dots$$

If we do the same process again and again, we conclude that

$$a_0 = f(0); a_1 = f'(0); a_2 = \frac{f''(0)}{2!}; a_3 = \frac{f'''(0)}{3!}; \dots; a_n = \frac{f^{(n)}(0)}{n!}.$$

Now, we obtain the Maclaurin series by substituting the values of $a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3,$ etc.

$$f(x) = f(0) + \frac{f'(0)}{1!}x + \frac{f''(0)}{2!}x^2 + \frac{f'''(0)}{3!}x^3 + \dots = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^{(n)}(0)}{n!}x^n.$$

By making the power series into general form, we get

$$f(x) = b_0 + b_1(x - a) + b_2(x - a)^2 + b_3(x - a)^3 + \dots$$

By substituting $b_n = \frac{f^{(n)}(a)}{n!}$ for $n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$, in the general power series, we get

$$\text{Taylor series: } f(x) = f(a) + \frac{f'(a)}{1!}(x - a) + \frac{f''(a)}{2!}(x - a)^2 + \frac{f'''(a)}{3!}(x - a)^3 + \dots$$

3. Application of Geometric Series and Maclaurin Series

Theorem 3.1: The sum of alternative harmonic series is equal to $\ln 2$.

$$i. e. \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} = \ln 2.$$

Case i: This theorem is proved using the geometric series.

$$\text{Let } S = 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots$$

$$\Rightarrow xS = x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + x^8 + \dots$$

$$\text{Then, } (S - xS) = 1 \Rightarrow (1 - x)S = 1 \Rightarrow \frac{1}{1 - x} = S.$$

$$i. e. \frac{1}{1 - x} = 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots$$

Integrating on both sides with respect to x :

$$\int \frac{1}{1 - x} dx = \int (1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots) dx.$$

$$\text{First, let us find the solution of } \int \frac{1}{1 - x} dx.$$

$$\text{Let } u = 1 - x; du = -dx; dx = -du.$$

$$\text{Then, } \int \frac{1}{1 - x} dx = - \int \frac{1}{u} du = - \ln u = - \ln(1 - x).$$

$$\text{Now, } \int (1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots) dx = - \ln(1 - x).$$

$$\Rightarrow x + \frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{x^3}{3} + \frac{x^4}{4} + \frac{x^5}{5} + \frac{x^6}{6} + \frac{x^7}{7} + \frac{x^8}{8} + \dots = - \ln(1 - x).$$

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{n} \dots = - \ln(1 - x) \Rightarrow - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{n} = \ln(1 - x).$$

Substituting $x = -1$ on both sides:

$$- \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n} = \ln(1 - (-1)) \Rightarrow \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n} = \ln 2 \quad \text{OR} \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} = \ln 2.$$

Case ii: Again, this theorem is proved using the Maclaurin series

Let us consider the function: $f(x) = \ln(1 + x)$.

If $x = 0$ in $(x) = \ln(1 + x)$, then $f(0) = \ln(1 + 0) = \ln 1 = 0$.

Now, by differentiating the function $f(x) = \ln(1 + x)$ and using $x = 0$, we obtain

$$f'(x) = \frac{1}{1+x} = (1+x)^{-1} \text{ and } f'(0) = \frac{1}{1+0} = (1+0)^{-1} = 1.$$

$$f''(x) = -(1+x)^{-2} \text{ and } f''(0) = -(1+0)^{-2} = -1 = -(1!).$$

$$f'''(x) = -2(1+x)^{-3} \text{ and } f'''(0) = -2(1+0)^{-3} = -2 = -(2!).$$

$$f^{iv}(x) = (-2) \times (-3)(1+x)^{-4} \text{ and } f^{iv}(0) = 3!(1+0)^{-3} = 3!.$$

$$f^v(x) = (-2) \times (-3) \times (-4)(1+x)^{-5} \text{ and } f^v(0) = -(4!).$$

Similarly, we can continue this process infinitely.

$$\text{Maclaurin series: } f(x) = f(0) + \frac{f'(0)}{1!}x + \frac{f''(0)}{2!}x^2 + \frac{f'''(0)}{3!}x^3 + \dots$$

$$\text{Then, } \ln(1+x) = 0 + \frac{1}{1!}x - \frac{1!}{2!}x^2 + \frac{2!}{3!}x^3 - \frac{3!}{4!}x^4 + \frac{4!}{5!}x^5 - \frac{5!}{6!}x^6 + \dots$$

$$\ln(1+x) = x - \frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{x^3}{3} - \frac{x^4}{4} + \frac{x^5}{5} - \frac{x^6}{6} + \dots$$

By substituting $x = 1$ in the series $\ln(1+x)$, we conclude that

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} = \ln 2.$$

4. Conclusion

In the article, the author expressed application of the geometric series and Maclaurin series. This idea can enable the scientific researchers for further involvement in research and development.

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